

PROGRESS IN PREPARATION AND DEFORMATION PROCESSING
OF SiC/Al COMPOSITES

A.P. Divecha

C.R. Crowe

S.G. Fishman

Naval Surface Weapons Center
White Oak, Silver Spring, MD 20910

Properties of whisker reinforced composites are impressive and, as a result, have been of interest to design engineers for many years. However, due to the high cost of whisker reinforcement, such metal matrix composites have been priced too high to be seriously considered as structural materials. In addition techniques for working and joining both continuous and discontinuous reinforced metal matrix composites are not well established, which also has served to drive up the price of such materials. Recently, the development of a potentially low cost SiC whisker coupled with low cost composite production techniques has resulted in the development of a family of promising SiC/Al composites with few of the drawbacks of other reinforced materials. Unlike most other continuous and discontinuous metal matrix composites, SiC/Al can be processed on conventional equipment using standard metal working techniques. It has been demonstrated that these composites can be easily forged, rolled, extruded, swaged, etc., into representative shapes such as tees, sheets, rods, and tubes. Such joining techniques as spot welding, friction welding, brazing and diffusion bonding are also amenable to SiC/Al composites. These aspects, coupled with the potential of low cost SiC whiskers (\$5 to \$10/lb) make it highly probable that such composites can be developed into a useful, high performance material with numerous applications where high strength and high stiffness to weight properties are important.

This paper presents the results of the research and developmental efforts on SiC/Al at the Naval Surface Weapons Center. The initial emphasis was on demonstration that a given aluminum alloy composite can be successfully reinforced with the potentially cheap SiC whiskers. (Initial work used 2024 Al as the matrix. This selection was based on the fact that 2024 Al is a well known and widely used alloy available in many useful shapes which can be aged to T4 and T6 conditions to attain fairly high strength levels.) It was reported in an earlier paper that strengths as high as 641 MPa (93 Ksi) were attained in a 2024-T4-25 v/o SiC whisker composite. Other tensile properties obtained were up to 0.9% elongation to fracture and Young's modulus of up to 170 GN/m² (24.7 x 10⁶ psi). Fracture toughness on unextruded composites ranged from K_{IC} values of 8 to 13 MN/m^{3/2}. Stress corrosion cracking (S.C.C.) tests showed that the composites are not very susceptible to S.C.C. in NaCl contaminated moist air.

A significant effort is now being directed at 5000 series aluminum alloys. In particular, 5456 Al is being investigated because it is a weldable, cor-

rosion resistant solid solution alloy used in a wide variety of shipboard applications. It has been demonstrated that the billet synthesis method utilized for 2024 matrix composites is also suitable for 5456 Al. Properties of extruded and rolled 5456 Al composites containing 25 v/o SiC whiskers will be presented. Yield and ultimate tensile strength, fracture toughness, and elastic modulus (acoustic and mechanical) will be presented and compared with similar data on 2024-T4 and 2024-T6 composites.

Also, information on the properties of joints made via friction welding, spot welding, etc., will be presented. Potential applications of the composites will be discussed.